

Misleading editorial on vitamin C in JAMA by Kalil (2020)

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Comment on:

Kalil AC.

Lack of Benefit of High-Dose Vitamin C, Thiamine, and Hydrocortisone Combination for Patients With Sepsis.

JAMA. 2020 Feb 4;323(5):419-420.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31950983>

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In the editorial on vitamin C in JAMA [1], Kalil writes: “*The reported mortality rates were in favor of vitamin C in the other 2 trials [2,3], although in one of those trials [2], the sample size was small (28 patients).*”

This misleads readers. Logically, a small sample size cannot explain a statistically significant benefit ($P = 0.01$; based on 2/14 vs. 9/14) reported by Zabet [2]. A small sample size can cause a false negative result because of the low statistical power. However, the risk of a false positive finding is not increased when the sample size gets smaller.

Kalil continues the same sentence: “*The reported mortality rates were in favor of vitamin C in the other 2 trials ... and in the other trial [3], mortality was not the primary outcome and lack of adjustment for multiple testing weakened the inference for the mortality outcome*”

This comment on the CITRIS-ALI trial [3] is also misleading as shown in two papers [4,5].

Kalil also writes: “*Vitamin C has now been evaluated as a treatment for sepsis and septic shock, either alone or in combination, in 8 RCTs ... Of the 8 RCTs, 6 (including a total of 633 patients) showed no significant effect of vitamin C on mortality [6,7,8,9,10,11]*”

Although Kalil speculated that small sample size might explain one positive result (see above), here Kalil ignores that “no significant effect” can simply be explained by the fact that the sample

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

size was small. Based on the confidence intervals, 5 of the 6 trials to which Kalil refers are non-informative (see the data and the statistical printouts after the references):

95% CI for mortality in vitC group	Trial
0.69-2.1	Galley (1997) [6]
0.60-3.7	Ferrón-Celma (2009) [7]
0.37-2.7	Schneider (2011) [8]
0.32-1.5	Fowler (2014) [9]
0.36-1.2	Nabil Habib (2017) [10]

A decrease in mortality by 10-20% can be clinically relevant when the intervention is a safe and very cheap essential nutrient. None of the above 5 small trials refutes such an effect. Only 1 of the cited 6 references had sample size that was large enough to give an informative result on mortality in their specific clinical context [11]. However, that trial should not be considered without simultaneously considering the highly significant benefits in the CITRIS-ALI trial [3-5] and the Zabet trial [2].

Furthermore, two of Kalil's "vitamin C" studies were not studies about vitamin C. Galley administered vitamin E and N-acetylcysteine together with vitamin C [6]. Schneider administered vitamin E, selenium, and many other substances together with vitamin C [8]. Harmful interaction between vitamin C and vitamin E was observed among middle-aged males of the large ATBC Study [12] and therefore vitamin E should not be assumed inactive when administered with vitamin C. Thus, Kalil included trials that did not focus on vitamin C.

Finally, the statement by Kalil that "6 [RCTs](including a total of 633 patients)" is false. The actual number of participants in the 6 trials was just 448 (based on 30+20+58+24+100+216 in the order of the references, see bottom). Thus, by referring to 5 non-informative small trials and claiming more participants than actually had been investigated, Kalil makes it seem that the potential benefit of vitamin C for sepsis patients has been widely refuted.

A further way by which Kalil misleads readers is by focusing only on mortality. There are other outcomes that are relevant for critically ill patients.

A meta-analysis of ICU trials calculated that "In 12 trials with 1766 patients, vitamin C reduced the length of ICU stay on average by 7.8% (95% CI: 4.2% to 11.2%; $p = 0.00003$)... In three trials in which patients needed mechanical ventilation for over 24 hours, vitamin C shortened the duration of mechanical ventilation by 18.2% (95% CI 7.7% to 27%; $p = 0.001$)" [13]

Another meta-analysis calculated that "In the non-US cardiac surgery trials, vitamin C decreased the length of hospital stay by 12.6% (95% CI 8.4–16.8%) and ICU stay by 8.0% (95% CI 3.0–13.0%). The US trials found no effect on hospital stay and ICU stay" [14]

These findings were dismissed by Kahil [1].

This is not the first case when JAMA has misled its readers about vitamin C.

In 1975, JAMA published an RCT on vitamin C for the common cold by Thomas Karlowski, Thomas Chalmers et al. [15], which has been widely cited as evidence that vitamin C is ineffective. However, the statistical analysis of that study was flawed [16,17].

In 1975, JAMA also published a review on vitamin C for the common cold by Michael Dykes and Paul Meier [18], which has also been highly influential. However, the review was biased and misled readers [16,19]. Linus Pauling wrote another review in which he presented the results of relevant trials and his own interpretations, and criticism of Dykes and Meier's arguments. Pauling submitted his manuscript to JAMA, but his paper was rejected even after Pauling twice made revisions to meet the suggestions of the referees. The manuscript was finally published in a minor journal [20,21]. The rejection of Pauling's review was an unfortunate decision by JAMA, as it prevented the readers from seeing the other side of an important scientific controversy.

In 1987, JAMA published an official statement by the American Medical Association "*One of the most widely misused vitamins is ascorbic acid. There is no reliable evidence that large doses of ascorbic acid prevent colds or shorten their duration*" [22]. That statement was based wholly on Thomas Chalmers' review [23]. However, there were significant errors also in this review, most notably in the extraction of data and in the calculations [16,24].

Finally, obfuscation in the reporting of the CITRIS-ALI trial findings in JAMA [3] was described in detail [4,5], and severe biases in the associated editorial were pointed out [25].

Thus, the editorial by Kalil [1] was not the first time when JAMA has been misleading its readers on vitamin C.

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Statistical printouts for the very small vitamin C trials [6-10]

Galley (1997) riskratio(11, 8, 16, 14) Disease Nondisease Total Exposed 11 5 16 Nonexposed 8 6 14

95 percent confidence interval: 0.69 2.11 sample estimates: [1] 1.2

Ferron (2009) riskratio(6, 4, 10, 10) Disease Nondisease Total Exposed 6 4 10 Nonexposed 4 6 10

95 percent confidence interval: 0.6 3.7 sample estimates: [1] 1.5

Schneider (2011) riskratio(6, 6, 29, 29) Disease Nondisease Total Exposed 6 23 29 Nonexposed 6 23 29

95 percent confidence interval: 0.37 2.74 sample estimates: [1] 1

Fowler (2014) riskratio(7, 5, 16, 8) Disease Nondisease Total Exposed 7 9 16 Nonexposed 5 3 8

95 percent confidence interval: 0.32 1.52 sample estimates: [1] 0.7

Nabil (2017) riskratio(12, 18, 50, 50) Disease Nondisease Total Exposed 12 38 50 Nonexposed 18 32 50

95 percent confidence interval: 0.36 1.23 sample estimates: [1] 0.67

The number of participants in the cited 6 RCTs [6-11] does not sum up to 633, although Kalil claims so [1]

	vit C	Placebo	Totals
Galley	16	14	30
Ferron	10	10	20
Schneider	29	29	58
Fowler	16	8	24
Nabil	50	50	100
Fujii	109	107	216
	230	218	448